

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable 3.3. Defined ToLCNDV-resistant tomato and cucurbit varieties (M54, DEM, PU)

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Defined ToLCNDV-resistant tomato and cucurbit varieties

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

24 h – 24 hours

DPI – Days post inoculation

NRI – Natural Resources Institute

PCR – Polymerase chain reaction

qPCR – Quantitative PCR

ToLCBV – Tomato leaf curl Bangalore virus

ToLCNDV – Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus

Ty – Tomato yellow leaf curl resistance allele

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Minimum 1 page to write here, it is required for dissemination purposes (i.e. the publishable summary of confidential deliverables has to be uploaded on the VIRTIGATION project website). Write here only information from confidential deliverables that you can share publicly.

Since its initial report from India in 1995, the tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) has been reported from at least a dozen Asian countries, expanding both in geography and host range to infect over 100 plant species. The virus was inadvertently introduced into Europe in 2014 and since been causing a major epidemic of leaf curl disease of cucurbit crops, causing severe economic losses to the growers in at least 10 European countries. ToLCNDV has been predicted to spread worldwide and cause diseases in tomatoes and several other crops. Deploying virus-resistant crops varieties is the most sustainable way of managing ToLCNDV. To mitigate the threat of ToLCNDV on the EU tomato sector, we screened five pre-breeding near isogenic tomato lines each carrying known resistance alleles such as Ty-1, Ty-3, Ty-4 and Ty-5 either singly or in combinations of more than one allele in identical genetic background. We found that Ty-1 and Ty-3 singly, and Ty-345 in combinations suppressed the multiplication of ToLCNDV. This is great news because most of these alleles are already bred into the EU tomato varieties and thus can withstand ToLCNDV pressure in Europe when that happens. In addition, and as a future pre-emptive breeding measure, we also screened the same five tomato lines to another commonly occurring begomovirus in India – tomato leaf curl Bangalore virus (ToLCBV). Among these tomato lines, only those carrying Ty-1 showed some levels of resistance to ToLCBV (50 % infection), while others showed varying levels of infection. These results, while show promising trends for ToLCNDV in tomatoes but also highlight the diverse responses of the existing tomato virus resistance alleles to different viruses and thus the potential threat of viruses causing damage to EU tomato sector remains high.

We also screened seven melon lines for resistance to ToLCNDV and they showed very high levels of resistance, which can be categorized as immune, which is extremely good news for future melon breeding in the EU.

2 INTRODUCTION – SCREENING TOMATO LINES FOR RESISTANCE TO TWO BEGOMOVIRUSES

2.1 Tomato lines

The five pre-breeding tomato lines were developed by the Volcani Centre Israel as part of their tomato breeding programme and sent to NRI-UK for screening against the Indian begomoviruses (ToLCNDV and ToLCBV) (Table 1). The Indian viruses are quarantine pests in Israel and thus the lines could not be evaluated in Israel, and the neutral country like the UK with necessary quarantine facilities and permissions was the ideal place for this task.

Table 1. Israeli tomato lines with unique resistance alleles tested for resistance to ToLCNDV and ToLCBV.

Sample	Allele(s) present
VC101	Ty-1
VC103	Ty-3
VC105	Ty-5
VC150	Ty-1 and Ty-5
VC345	Ty-3, Ty-4 and Ty-5
MoneyMaker	None, a control EU variety

2.2 Virus inoculation

Inoculation of viruses by the whiteflies was the most natural way of testing them because these viruses are spread by whiteflies in field conditions. A colony of the whitefly species, Asia II-7 was developed in the NRI quarantine facilities and simultaneously both virus source plants and the test varieties were grown. About 200 adult whiteflies were collected from the colony and released separately onto the tomato plants infected with ToLCNDV and ToLCBV. The viruses themselves were collected originally from India and Bangladesh and maintained at NRI quarantine facility.

The whiteflies were allowed to feed on virus-infected plants for 24 h (virus acquisition period) and about 10 adults were transferred onto each test plant covered in cylindrical tubes. These flies inoculated the plants for a further 24 h (virus inoculation period). The flies were then removed from the plants and they were incubated in the quarantine lab for one month for the expression of symptoms. Between 13 and 17 plants were inoculated with ToLCNDV while about 6-10 plants were tested for ToLCBV. The number of plants that exhibited symptoms and the severity of symptoms was recorded at weekly intervals. The following severity score was adapted:

- 0 = No symptoms
- 1 = Mild symptoms
- 2 = Severe symptoms, and
- 3 = Very severe symptoms

For robustness of the results and additional confirmation, the presence of the virus was detected either by PCR or qPCR 40 days after virus inoculation.

2.3 Resistance levels of tomato lines with unique alleles

2.3.1 Resistance to New Delhi virus - ToLCNDV

Based on visual scoring of symptoms, lines carrying VC101 and VC150 alleles did not show any symptoms while all plants of VC105 and the susceptible control were infected (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. The visual scoring of ToLCNDV symptoms on tomato lines.

However, when five randomly selected plants were tested by PCR, all plants of VC101, VC103, VC105 and Moneymaker tested positive (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Gel electrophoresis of PCR amplified ToLCNDV DNA fragments. Where lanes 1-5 and 9-13 were inoculated plants, while lanes 6 and 8 were empty wells, and lane 7 had the negative control. A = Moneymaker, B = VC101, C = VC105, D = VC103 and M = Molecular weight marker (Gene Ruler Express).

We therefore further carried out qPCR on a total of eight plants per line at 20, 30 and 40 days after virus inoculation. The qPCR results gave more nuanced results in terms of the quantities of the virus present in each line (Figure 3) with VC101 and VC103 on average showing lowest amount of the virus, while the control plants Moneymaker showed the highest amount of ToLCNDV. A declining trend of virus accumulation was observed.

Figure 3. Israeli tomato lines showing ToLCNDV concentration at 20, 30 and 40 days post inoculation (DPI).

2.3.2 Resistance to Bengaluru virus - ToLCBV

An identical experiment was conducted in which ToLCBV was used (Table 2, Figure 4).

Table 2. Incidence of ToLCBV on Israeli tomato lines.

Sample	PCR positive	% infection
VC101	4/8	50.0
VC103	10/10	100.0
VC105	9/10	90.0
VC150	5/7	71.4
VC345	7/10	70.0
MoneyMaker	6/6	100

Figure 4. PCR results on ToLCBV inoculated plants of Israeli tomato lines. The names of lines and the sample numbers are labelled.

2.3.3 Resistance of melons to ToLCNDV

To test for the resistance of melon lines to ToLCNDV, seven lines were obtained from INRAE (Table 3) and screened for resistance to ToLCNDV by whitefly inoculations as described above.

Table 3. Melon lines tested for resistance to ToLCNDV inoculations

Variety	Control non-inoculated plants	Total inoculated plants
Cucumber var. Marketer (susceptible control)	03	11
IC-274014	02	08
WM7	03	11
WM9	01	04
AM87	03	10

PI- 179901	01	02
PI-282448	03	11
PI- 124112	03	11

Symptoms was recorded at 10, 20, 30 and 40 days after virus inoculation and found none of the melon lines showed any sign of virus symptoms while the susceptible cucumber var. Marketmore showed severe symptoms with 100% infection rate.

The plants were also tested for virus by PCR and found that none of the melon lines tested supported high levels of virus while the susceptible cucumber had very high virus titre (Figure 5, Table 4).

Figure 5. Graph showing average virus copy number compared to plant DNA, 40 days after virus inoculation. Since the virus copy numbers in melon lines were very low, the below table 4 is provided for showing additional data points.

Table 4. Average virus to plant DNA ratio at 20- and 40-days post inoculation of INRAE melons with ToLCNDV.

Variety	Average virus/plant DNA ratio at 20 DPI	Average virus/plant DNA ratio at 40 DPI
Cucumber cv. Marketeer	840.582	201.089
WM 7	0.015	0.551
PI-282448	0.0871	0.003
PI- 124112	0.004	0.002
IC-274014	0.009	0.229

PI- 179901	0.001	1.325
AM 87	0.236	0.001
WM 9	0.002	0.006

2.3.4 Conclusions

All the tomato lines carrying virus resistance alleles showed higher levels of resistance compared to the susceptible control Moneymaker in terms of reduced disease incidences, and reduced virus titre. However, the % incidence of disease and the quantities varied. While this is encouraging but none of the lines were completely immune to either virus, which indicates the need for continued search for resistance alleles both in the EU and countries like India because of the damage they can cause to growers and potential threat of their introduction to new countries. In contrast, it is extremely positive results for melons because all the seven melon lines screened very high levels of resistance, they are almost immune to ToLCNDV.